

CONTROLLABILITY OF NONLINEAR IMPULSIVE INTEGRO-DIFFERENTIAL FRACTIONAL TIME-INVARIANT SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT. We consider controllability of nonlinear impulsive integro-differential fractional time-invariant systems. We first give a solution expression for linear impulsive fractional time-invariant systems. By the Schauder fixed point theorem, sufficient conditions for the controllability of nonlinear impulsive integro-differential fractional time-invariant systems are obtained.

1. Introduction. Fractional differential equations are generalizations of classical differential equations which have proved to be an excellent instrument for the description of memory and hereditary properties of various materials and processes. They occur frequently in various fields of science and engineering such as porous media, diffusion and transport theory, chaos and turbulence, signal processing, fractional control, description of soft materials, and analysis of power law phenomena. There has been significant theoretical development in fractional differential equations in recent years (see [15, 25]) and the subject has attracted widespread attention (see [1, 2, 17, 18, 32, 37]).

In 1960, Kalman first introduced the concept of controllability, which leads to some very important conclusions regarding the behavior of linear and nonlinear dynamical systems. It is well known that the controllability plays a significant role in the modern control theory and engineering, since they are closely related to pole assignment, structural decomposition, and quadratic optimal control. There are

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various works on controllability of systems represented by differential equations, integro-differential equations, differential inclusions, neutral functional differential equations and impulsive differential inclusions in Banach spaces (see [6, 7, 8]). A standard approach is to transform the controllability problem into a fixed point problem for an appropriate operator in a functional space. There are many papers devoted to the controllability problem in which authors used the theory of fractional calculus and a fixed point approach [19, 20, 21, 22, 23]. Different techniques have also been developed to investigate the controllability of various systems, such as geometric analysis [24, 30], Lie algebraic approach [28], functional analysis [9], and algebraic method [26, 34].

Recently, the fractional dynamical systems have attracted lots of attention in control systems. More and more people have focused on the controllability of fractional dynamical systems. For more details, we refer to [4, 12, 31].

In [12], T.L. Guo investigated the following controllability and observability of impulsive fractional linear time-invariant system:

$$\begin{cases} {}^c D_t^q x(t) = Ax(t) + Bu(t), & t \in [0, T] \setminus \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_k\}, \\ \Delta x(t_i) = I_i(t_i, x(t_i)), \\ y(t) = Cx(t) + Du(t), \\ x(0) = x_0, \end{cases}$$

where ${}^c D_t^q$ is the Caputo fractional derivative of order $0 < q \leq 1$, A , B , C and D are constant matrices, $x \in R^n$ is the state variable, $u \in R^m$ is the control input, $y \in R^p$ is the output, $I_i : \Omega \rightarrow R^n$, $T < +\infty$.

In [4], K. Balachandran, J.Y. Park and J.J. Trujillo considered the controllability of nonlinear fractional dynamical systems and nonlinear fractional integro-differential systems:

$$\begin{cases} {}^c D_t^\alpha x(t) = Ax(t) + Bu(t) + f(t, x(t), u(t)), & t \in [0, b], \\ x(0) = x_0, \end{cases}$$

and

$$\begin{cases} {}^c D_t^\alpha x(t) = Ax(t) + Bu(t) + f(t, x(t), \int_0^t g(t, s, x(s)) ds), & t \in [0, b], \\ x(0) = x_0, \end{cases}$$

where $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, $x \in R^n$, $u \in R^m$ and A is an $n \times n$ matrix, B is an $n \times m$ matrix and $f : J \times R^n \times R^m \rightarrow R^n$, $g : J \times J \times R^n \rightarrow R^n$ are continuous functions.

In [31], J.R. Wang and Y. Zhou researched the complete controllability of fractional semilinear systems in infinite dimensional spaces of the type

$$\begin{cases} {}^c D_t^q x(t) = Ax(t) + Bu(t) + f(t, x(t)), & t \in [0, b], \\ x(0) = x_0, \end{cases}$$

where $0 < q \leq 1$, the state $x(\cdot)$ takes values in a Banach space X and the control function $u(\cdot)$ is given in $L^2(J, U)$ with U as a Banach space. A is the infinitesimal generator of a strongly continuous semigroup $T(t), t \geq 0$ in X , B is a bounded linear operator from U into X , and $f : J \times X \rightarrow X$ is a given X -value function.

Many real systems in physics, chemistry, biology, engineering, and information science may experience abrupt changes at certain instants during the dynamical process. These kinds of impulsive behaviors can be modeled by impulsive systems. The study of impulsive systems has seen a rapid development in the past few years. For the general theory and applications of impulsive systems, one can refer to the monographs of Deo et al. [11], Bainov et al. [3], Sandberg [27], Lakshmikantham et al. [16], and Wang et al. [33]. On the other hand, integro-differential equations arise in the linear theory of isotropic viscoelastic rods and plates. Recently, many works for the time-invariant integro-differential equation have been studied by various authors [4, 5, 7, 35, 36].

Motivated by the above works and the fact that nonlinear impulsive integro-differential fractional time-invariant systems have not been studied very extensively, we study the controllability of the following nonlinear impulsive integro-differential fractional time-invariant systems:

$$(1.1) \quad \begin{cases} {}^c D_t^q x(t) = Ax(t) + Bu(t) \\ \quad + f(t, x(t), \int_0^t h(t, s, x(s)) ds, u(t)), & t \in J \setminus \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_k\}, \\ \Delta x(t_i) = I_i(x(t_i)), \\ x(0) = x_0, \end{cases}$$

where $0 < q \leq 1, x \in R^n, u \in R^m$ and A is an $n \times n$ matrix, B is an $n \times m$ matrix and $f : J \times R^n \times R^n \times R^m \rightarrow R^n, h : J \times J \times R^n \rightarrow R^n$ are continuous functions. $I_i : R^n \rightarrow R^n$ is continuous for $i = 1, 2, \dots, k, J = [0, T], 0 = t_0 < t_1 < \dots < t_k < \dots < t_k < t_{k+1} = T, \Delta x(t_i) = x(t_i^+) - x(t_i^-)$, and $x(t_i^+)$ and $x(t_i^-)$ denote the right and left limits of $x(t)$ at $t = t_i (i = 1, 2, \dots, k)$. Our main result, stated as Theorem 3.1, provides the

controllability of system (1.1) under some general conditions by using the Schauder fixed point theorem.

The paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we give some necessary notations and present some definitions. In Section 3, by using the Schauder fixed point theorem, we obtain the condition of controllability of nonlinear impulsive integro-differential fractional time-invariant system.

2. Preliminaries. Let us introduce the spaces:

$$PC(J, R^n) = \{x : J \rightarrow R^n \mid x \in C(J_i, R^n), i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k, \\ \text{and } x(t_i^+), i = 1, 2, \dots, k\}$$

with the norm $\|x\|_{PC(J, R^n)} = \sup_{t \in J} |x(t)|$. Denote by Θ the Banach space of precise continuous $R^n \times R^m$ -valued functions defined on the interval J with the norm $\|(x, u)\| = \|x\|_{PC(J, R^n)} + \|u\|_{PC(J, R^m)}$, which is $\Theta = PC(J, R^n) \times PC(J, R^m)$.

For the convenience of the readers, we first present some useful definitions and fundamental facts of fractional calculus theory, which can be found in [13, 25].

Definition 2.1. For $q > 0$, the integral

$$I_t^q f(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(q)} \int_0^t \frac{f(s)}{(t-s)^{1-q}} ds$$

is called the Riemann-Liouville fractional integral of order q .

Definition 2.2. For a function f given in the interval $[0, \infty)$, the expression

$$D_t^q f(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-q)} \left(\frac{d}{dt}\right)^n \int_0^t \frac{f(s)}{(t-s)^{q-n+1}} ds, \quad n = [q] + 1,$$

is called the Riemann-Liouville fractional derivative of order $q > 0$.

Definition 2.3. The Caputo derivative of order q for a function $f : [0, \infty) \rightarrow R$ can be written as

$${}^c D_t^q f(t) = D^q \left[f(t) - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{t^k}{k!} f^{(k)}(0) \right], \quad t > 0, \quad n-1 < q < n.$$

Remark 2.4. (i) If $f^{(n)} \in C[0, \infty)$, then

$${}^c D_t^q f(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-q)} \int_0^t \frac{f^{(n)}(s)}{(t-s)^{q+1-n}} dt, \quad t > 0, \quad n-1 < q < n.$$

(ii) The Caputo derivative of a constant is equal to zero.

Definition 2.5. The Mittag-Leffler function in two parameters is defined as

$$E_{\alpha,\beta} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{\Gamma(\alpha k + \beta)}, \quad z \in \mathbb{C},$$

where $\alpha, \beta > 0$ and \mathbb{C} denotes the complex plane.

Remark 2.6. (i) For $\beta = 1$,

$$E_{\alpha}(\lambda z^{\alpha}) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\lambda^k z^{k\alpha}}{\Gamma(\alpha k + 1)}, \quad \lambda, z \in \mathbb{C}.$$

(ii) For $\beta = 1$,

$$E_{\alpha}(At^{\alpha}) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{A^k t^{k\alpha}}{\Gamma(\alpha k + 1)},$$

with the property ${}^c D_t^{\alpha} E_{\alpha}(At^{\alpha}) = A E_{\alpha}(At^{\alpha})$.

Consider the following linear impulsive fractional time-invariant system:

$$(2.1) \quad \begin{cases} {}^c D_t^q x(t) = Ax(t) + Bu(t), & t \in J \setminus \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_k\}, \\ \Delta x(t_i) = I_i(x(t_i)), \\ x(0) = x_0, \end{cases}$$

where $0 < q < 1$, $x \in R^n$, $u \in R^m$, A is an $n \times n$ matrix and B is an $n \times m$ matrix.

The solution of the system (2.1) can be represented by (see [3])

$$x(t) = \begin{cases} E_q(At^q)x_0 + \int_0^t (t-s)^{q-1} E_{q,q}(A(t-s)^q)Bu(s) ds, & t \in [0, t_1], \\ E_q(At^q)x_0 + \sum_{j=1}^i E_q(A(t-t_j)^q)I_j(x(t_j)) + \int_0^t (t-s)^{q-1} E_{q,q}(A(t-s)^q)Bu(s) ds, & t \in (t_i, t_{i+1}], \\ & i = 1, 2, \dots, k. \end{cases}$$

Definition 2.7. System (2.1) is called state controllable on $[0, t_f]$ (for $t_f \in (0, T]$) if for every $x_0, x_{t_f} \in R^n$ there exists a control $u(t)$ such that the solution $x(t)$ of (2.1) satisfies $x(t_f) = x_{t_f}$.

Theorem 2.8. [12] *The linear impulsive fractional system (2.1) is controllable on $[0, t_f]$ if and only if the controllability Grammian matrix*

$$W[0, t_f] = \int_0^{t_f} (t_f - s)^{q-1} [E_{q,q}(A(t_f - s)^q)B][E_{q,q}(A(t_f - s)^q)B]^* ds$$

is nonsingular, for some $t_f \in (0, T]$. Here $$ denotes the matrix transpose.*

3. A nonlinear impulsive integro-differential system. Consider the following nonlinear impulsive integro-differential fractional time-invariant system:

$$(3.1) \quad \begin{cases} {}^cD_t^q x(t) = Ax(t) + Bu(t) \\ \quad + f(t, x(t), \int_0^t h(t, s, x(s)) ds, u(t)), & t \in J \setminus \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_k\}, \\ \Delta x(t_i) = I_i(x(t_i)), \\ x(0) = x_0. \end{cases}$$

For each $(x, u) \in \Theta$, if $x \in PC(J, R^n)$ is a solution of the following linear impulsive fractional time-invariant system:

$$\begin{cases} {}^cD_t^q x(t) = Ax(t) + Bu(t) \\ \quad + f(t, x(t), \int_0^t h(t, s, x(s)) ds, u(t)), & t \in J \setminus \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_k\}, \\ \Delta x(t_i) = I_i(z(t_i)), \\ x(0) = x_0, \end{cases}$$

then x can be represented by

$$\begin{aligned} x(t) = E_q(At^q)x_0 + \int_0^t (t-s)^{q-1} E_{q,q}(A(t-s)^q)Bu(s) ds \\ + \int_0^t (t-s)^q E_{q,q}(A(t-s)^q) \\ \cdot f\left(s, z(s), \int_0^t h(t, s, z(s)) ds, v(s)\right) ds \end{aligned}$$

for $t \in [0, t_1]$, and

$$\begin{aligned}
 x(t) = & E_q(At^q)x_0 + \sum_{j=1}^i E_q(A(t-t_j)^q)I_j(z(t_j)) \\
 & + \int_0^t (t-s)^{q-1} E_{q,q}(A(t-s)^q)Bu(s) ds + \int_0^t (t-s)^q E_{q,q}(A(t-s)^q) \\
 & \cdot f\left(s, z(s), \int_0^t h(t, s, z(s)) ds, v(s)\right) ds
 \end{aligned}$$

for $t \in (t_i, t_{i+1}]$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, k$.

Now we make the following assumptions:

(H1) $f : J \times R^n \times R^n \times R^m \rightarrow R^n$, $h : J \times J \times R^n \rightarrow R^n$ are continuous functions and f satisfies the condition

$$\lim_{\|(x,u)\| \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\|f(t, x(t), \int_0^t h(t, s, x(s)) ds, u(t))\|}{\|(x, u)\|} = 0 \quad \text{uniformly in } t \in J.$$

(H2) The function $I_i : R^n \rightarrow R^n$ is continuous and

$$\lim_{\|x\| \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\|I_i(x)\|}{\|x\|} = 0.$$

Theorem 3.1. *Assume that (H1) and (H2) hold. If, in addition, the linear impulsive fractional time-invariant system (2.1) is controllable on $[0, t_f]$, then the nonlinear impulsive fractional system (3.1) is controllable on $[0, t_f]$ for some $t_f \in (0, T]$.*

Proof. We first define the operator $T : \Theta \rightarrow \Theta$ by $T(z, v) = (x, u)$, where

$$\begin{aligned}
 u(t) = & B^* E_{q,q}(A^*(t_f-t)^q)W^{-1}[0, t_f] \\
 & \cdot \left[x_{t_f} - E_q(A(t_f)^q)x_0 - \int_0^{t_f} (t_f-s)^{q-1} E_{q,q}(A(t_f-s)^q) \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \cdot f\left(s, z(s), \int_0^t h(t, s, z(s)) ds, v(s)\right) ds \right],
 \end{aligned}$$

for $t_f \in [0, t_1]$, and for $t_f \in (t_i, t_{i+1}]$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, k$,

$$\begin{aligned}
u(t) = & B^* E_{q,q}(A^*(t_f - t)^q) W^{-1}[0, t_f] \\
& \cdot \left[x_{t_f} - E_q(A(t_f)^q)x_0 - \sum_{j=1}^i E_q(A(t_f - t_j)^q)I_j(z(t_j)) \right. \\
& \quad \left. - \int_0^{t_f} (t_f - s)^{q-1} E_{q,q}(A(t_f - s)^q) \right. \\
& \quad \left. \cdot f\left(s, z(s), \int_0^t h(t, s, z(s)) ds, v(s)\right) ds \right],
\end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
x(t) = & E_q(At^q)x_0 + \int_0^t (t-s)^{q-1} E_{q,q}(A(t-s)^q)Bu(s) ds \\
& + \int_0^t (t-s)^{q-1} E_{q,q}(A(t-s)^q) \\
& \quad \cdot f\left(s, z(s), \int_0^t h(t, s, z(s)) ds, v(s)\right) ds,
\end{aligned}$$

for $t \in [0, t_1]$, and for $t \in (t_i, t_{i+1}]$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, k$,

$$\begin{aligned}
x(t) = & E_q(At^q)x_0 + \sum_{j=1}^i E_q(A(t-t_j)^q)I_j(z(t_j)) \\
& + \int_0^t (t-s)^{q-1} E_{q,q}(A(t-s)^q)Bu(s) ds \\
& + \int_0^t (t-s)^{q-1} E_{q,q}(A(t-s)^q) \\
& \quad \cdot f\left(s, z(s), \int_0^t h(t, s, z(s)) ds, v(s)\right) ds.
\end{aligned}$$

Now take

$$\begin{aligned}
k_1 &= \max\{a_1 T^q \|B\| q^{-1}, 1\}, \\
a_1 &= \sup \|E_{q,q}(A(t_f - t)^q)\|, \quad a_2 = \sup \|E_q(At^q)x_0\|, \quad a_3 = \sup \|E_q(At^q)\|, \\
b_1 &= 8k_1 \|B^*\| a_1 \|W^{-1}\| \|x_{t_f}\|, \quad b_2 = 8k_1 \|B^*\| a_1 \|W^{-1}\| a_2, \\
c_1 &= 8k_1 k \|B^*\| a_1 \|W^{-1}\| a_3, \quad c_2 = 8k_1 \|B^*\| a_1^2 \|W^{-1}\| T^q q^{-1}, \\
d_1 &= 4a_2, \quad d_2 = 8k_1 k a_3, \quad d_3 = 8a_1 T^q q^{-1}, \\
b &= \max\{b_2, d_1\}, \quad \tilde{b} = \max\{b_1, d_1\}, \\
c &= \max\{c_2, d_3\}, \quad \tilde{c} = \max\{c_1, d_2\},
\end{aligned}$$

$$f^0 = \sup \left\{ \left| f \left(s, z(s), \int_0^t h(t, s, z(s)) ds, v(s) \right) \right| : s \in J \right\},$$

$$I^0 = \sup \{ |I_i(z(t_j))|, t_i \in J \}.$$

Thus, for all $t_f \in [0, T] \setminus \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_k\}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} |u(t)| &\leq \|B^*\| a_1 \|W^{-1}\| [\|x_{t_f}\| + a_2 + ka_3 I^0 + q^{-1} T^q a_1 f^0] \\ &\leq \frac{b_1}{8k_1} + \frac{b_2}{8k_1} + \frac{c_1}{8k_1} I^0 + \frac{c_2}{8k_1} f^0 \\ &\leq \frac{1}{8k_1} [\tilde{b} + \tilde{c} I^0 + b + c f^0], \\ |x(t)| &\leq a_2 + \frac{\|B\| a_1 T^q}{8k_1 q} [\tilde{b} + \tilde{c} I^0 + b + c f^0] + \frac{d_2}{8} I^0 + a_1 T^q q^{-1} f^0 \\ &\leq \frac{d_1}{4} + \frac{1}{8} [\tilde{b} + \tilde{c} I^0 + b + c f^0] + \frac{d_2}{8} I^0 + \frac{d_3}{8} f^0 \\ &\leq \frac{1}{4} [\tilde{b} + \tilde{c} I^0 + b + c f^0]. \end{aligned}$$

By Proposition 1 of [10], we know the functions f and I_i satisfy the conditions stated in that proposition.

Hence, for each pair of positive constants c, d and \tilde{c}, \tilde{d} , there exists a constant r , where $r \geq \max\{2d, 2\tilde{d}\}$, such that if $|(z, v)| \leq r$, then

$$(3.2) \quad c f^0 + d \leq r, \quad \tilde{c} I^0 + \tilde{d} \leq r \quad \text{for all } t \in J.$$

Now take c, d and \tilde{c}, \tilde{d} as given above, and let r be chosen so that the inequality (3.2) is satisfied. Therefore, let

$$\Theta(r) = \left\{ (z, v) \in \Theta : \|z\| \leq \frac{r}{2}, \|v\| \leq \frac{r}{2} \right\}.$$

We have $T : \Theta(r) \rightarrow \Theta(r)$. Since the functions f and I_i are continuous, it means that the operator T is continuous. By the Arzelà-Ascoli theorem, it is easy to check that the operator T is completely continuous.

Obviously, $\Theta(r)$ is closed, bounded and convex. By the Schauder fixed point theorem, we can conclude that T has a fixed point $(z, v) \in \Theta(r)$ such that

$$T(z, v) = (z, v) \equiv (x, u).$$

Hence, we have the following expressions for $x(t)$:

$$\begin{aligned}
 x(t) = E_q(At^q)x_0 + \int_0^t (t-s)^{q-1} E_{q,q}(A(t-s)^q) Bu(s) ds \\
 + \int_0^t (t-s)^{q-1} E_{q,q}(A(t-s)^q) \\
 \cdot f\left(s, x(s), \int_0^t h(t, s, x(s)) ds, u(s)\right) ds
 \end{aligned}$$

for $t \in [0, t_1]$, and for $t \in (t_i, t_{i+1}]$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, k$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 x(t) = E_q(At^q)x_0 + \sum_{j=1}^i E_q(A(t-t_j)^q) I_j(t_j, x(t_j)) \\
 + \int_0^t (t-s)^{q-1} E_{q,q}(A(t-s)^q) Bu(s) ds \\
 + \int_0^t (t-s)^{q-1} E_{q,q}(A(t-s)^q) \\
 \cdot f\left(s, x(s), \int_0^t h(t, s, x(s)) ds, u(s)\right) ds.
 \end{aligned}$$

So, $x(t)$ is the solution of (3.1).

Thus, if $t_f \in [0, t_1]$, it is easy to check that $x(t_f) = x_{t_f}$. Similarly, if $t_f \in (t_i, t_{i+1}]$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, k$, then $x(t_f) = x_{t_f}$. Consequently, the system (3.1) is controllable on $[0, t_f]$. \square

Remark 3.2. We make use of the following conditions:

(H₁') $f : J \times R^n \times R^n \rightarrow R^n$ and $h : J \times J \times R^n \rightarrow R^n$ are continuous functions and there exists a constant L_1 such that

$$\left| f\left(t, x(t), \int_0^t h(t, s, x(s)) ds\right) \right| \leq L_1 \quad \text{for all } t, s \in J, x \in PC(J, R^n).$$

(H₂') The function $I_i : R^n \rightarrow R^n$ is continuous and there exists a constant L_2 such that $|I_i(x)| \leq L_2$ for all $x \in R^n$.

In addition, assume that the linear impulsive fractional time-invariant system (2.1) is controllable on $[0, t_f]$. By the Schauder fixed point theorem, we can also derive that the following nonlinear impulsive integro-differential fractional system (3.3) is controllable on $[0, t_f]$:

$$(3.3) \quad \begin{cases} {}^c D_t^q x(t) = Ax(t) + Bu(t) \\ \quad + f(t, x(t), \int_0^t h(t, s, x(s)) ds), & t \in J \setminus \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_k\}, \\ \Delta x(t_i) = I_i(x(t_i)), \\ x(0) = x_0. \end{cases}$$

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